

VARIATION IN HABITAT CHARACTERISTICS AND THE OCCURRENCE OF *NOTHOBRANCHIUS* SPECIES IN SEASONAL BIOTOPES OF TANZANIA

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The authors independently conducted field studies three weeks apart on some of the same *Nothobranchius* biotopes in eastern Tanzania, visiting the same sites in January (Nagy) and February (Horváth Kis), 2009. This report describes changes in habitats and species between the visits, with comments on factors that may have contributed to the changes. The study sites are illustrated in Figure 1 and the locality data are summarized in Table 1.

Tanzania, south of the Equator in East Africa, is a country of lakes, mountains and savannah, with a diverse flora and fauna, much of it protected in national parks. Tanzania's Mount Kilimanjaro is the highest point in Africa, Lake Tanganyika is the longest and deepest lake of the continent, and Lake Victoria is the world's

second largest lake. Tanzania is dominated by the 900–1800 meter high plateau of the East African Highland, and divided by the Great Rift Valley. Habitat diversity ranges from hot semi-deserts to year-round ice at the top of Kilimanjaro. Most of Tanzania is woodland or grassland savannah, a typical tropical ecosystem.

Northeastern and eastern Tanzania usually have two rainy seasons a year. The Masika, the longer rainy season, occurs in March through May, and the shorter Vuli rainy season occurs from October to mid-December. During the rainy seasons, rivers often overflow the banks and inundate adjacent floodplains. Periodic flooding is essential for survival of *Nothobranchius* species that typically occur in ephemeral aquatic habitats that disappear in the dry seasons.

Figure 1: Map showing the *Nothobranchius* localities investigated by both authors during separate field trips in early 2009.

Variability of *Nothobranchius* species in the habitats

Over cons, geomorphological processes modify major rivers, tributaries, and adjacent flood plains. The river's inhabitants adapt and change over time and new

species may develop through genetic isolation that favors adaptive traits (Watters, 2006a and 2006b). In the shorter term of a few years, extreme floods or extreme drought can influence distribution of a species. Regular annual and seasonal flooding affects the distribution of species in in-

dividual rivers and in multiple river basins (Watters, 2006b).

Over years, topography, climate, and seasonal rainfall affect the location of a river bed and the capacity of its flood plain catchments. Within the river, current-driven shifts in sediment accumulations continually change the locations of the riffles, runs, and pools of the stream bed and the locations of the adjacent flood plain pools (Williams, 2006).

Every year, the most fundamental habitat fluctuations are caused by regular rainy and dry seasons. When the flood plain pools dry out, the species survives as fertilized eggs deposited in the substratum during the prior wet season. We found just this condition on the west side of the

road from Dar es Salaam at about 1 km before Bagamoyo (Locality 'a' on Figure 1). In January 2009, Nagy collected *Nothobranchius melanospilus* from a shallow pool, and in February 2009 Horváth Kis found only a dried mud substratum.

When a habitat has dried out, it may seem obvious why no adult fishes are found, but what is logical may not be correct. In some cases we observed adult *Nothobranchius* had entirely disappeared from an existing pool or their numbers were greatly reduced over a short period, yet the pool remained. The localities described below represent cases where sufficient water was in the habitat at the time of both visits to sustain fishes.

Figure 2: Locality Ruvu River TZN 09–4. Photo taken 12 January, 2009 by Béla Nagy.

Figure 3. *Nothobranchius janpapi* Ruvu River TZN 09–4. Wild-caught male. Photo by Béla Nagy.

Figure 4. Locality Ruvu River TZN 09–4. Photo taken 1 February, 2009 by András Horváth Kis.

Description of the localities

Ruvu River

Nothobranchius locations are known from many Ruvu River flood plain pools alongside the Dar es Salaam to Morogoro road. We examined variation at two sites.

The first site was a temporary pool a few kilometers from the Ruvu River towards Morogoro (Locality 'b' in Figure 1 and Table 1). During the first visit in January the pool was 10 x 5 m, with a shallow embayment protected by overhanging grasses (Figure 2). *Nothobranchius janpapi* (Figure 3) and *Nothobranchius melanospilus* occurred beneath the protective grasses, while cichlids occurred elsewhere in the pool. In February the habitat had become smaller and the protected embayment had dried out (Figure 4). No *Nothobranchius* species were found.

The second site was on the opposite side of the river, 1.4 km past the Ruvu River bridge in the direction of Dar es Salaam (Locality 'c' on Figure 1 and Table 1). During January a few *Nothobranchius annectens*, *Nothobranchius janpapi*, and *Nothobranchius melanospilus* were collected in a pool about 5 x 10 m (Figures 5 and 6) under thorny branches hanging into the water on one side of the pool. Numerous cichlids were also captured. In February, no *Nothobranchius* species were collected at the site, although cichlid fry and adults were common.

Yombo

The single Yombo locality investigated was an extensive temporary pool about 1 m deep, adjacent to a dirt road along the Ruvu River between Bagamoyo and the Dar es Salaam-Morogoro road (Locality 'd'

Table 1: Compilation of locality data including a comparison of water quality parameters measured during the successive field trips.

Location on the map	Geographic designation	Coordinates	Location code	Collection date	<i>Nothobranchius</i> species	pH	TDS ppm	°C
a	Bagamoyo	06°27.638' S; 38°54.439' E	TZN 09-1	12 Jan 2009	<i>N. melanospilus</i>	7.42	215	26.9
			-	1 Feb 2009	-	-	-	-
b	Ruvu River	06°40.818' S; 38°39.829' E	TZN 09-4	12 Jan 2009	<i>N. janpapi</i> , <i>N. melanospilus</i>	7.72	146	31.0
			-	1 Feb 2009	-	-	-	-
c	Ruvu River	06°41.901' S; 38°42.252' E	TZN 09-5	12 Jan 2009	<i>N. annectens</i> , <i>N. janpapi</i> , <i>N. melanospilus</i>	7.40	145	31.4
			-	1 Feb 2009	-	-	-	-
d	Yombo	06°41.548' S; 38°45.183' E	TZN 09-2	12 Jan 2009	<i>N. melanospilus</i>	7.67	93	31.0
			TZHK 09-2	1 Feb 2009	<i>N. melanospilus</i>	7.28	80	34.9
e	Lukwale River	07°11.231' S; 39°10.306' E	TZN 09-8	13 Jan 2009	<i>N. albimarginatus</i> , <i>N. melanospilus</i> , <i>N. ruudwildekampi</i>	7.39	215	27.8
			TZHK 09-3	2 Feb 2009	<i>N. melanospilus</i> , <i>N. ruudwildekampi</i>	5.88	570	28.4
f	Mbezi River	07°11.617' S; 39°10.299' E	TZN 09-9	13 Jan 2009	<i>N. albimarginatus</i> , <i>N. luekei</i> , <i>N. melanospilus</i> , <i>N. ruudwildekampi</i>	7.19	156	29.1
			TZHK 09-4	2 Feb 2009	<i>N. luekei</i>	6.79	137	30.2
g	Jaribu	07°31.949' S; 39°07.879' E	TZN 09-11	14 Jan 2009	<i>N. ruudwildekampi</i>	7.64	222	32.4
			TZHK 09-6	2 Feb 2009	<i>N. ruudwildekampi</i>	6.30	136	28.8

Figure 5. Locality Ruvu River TZN 09–5. Photo taken 12 January, 2009 by Béla Nagy.

Figure 6. *Nothobranchius annectens* Ruvu River TZN 09–5. Wild-caught male. Photo by Béla Nagy.

Figure 7. Locality Yombo TZN 09–2. Photo taken 12 January, 2009 by Béla Nagy.

on Figure 1 and Table 1). In January (Figure 7), many pale and thin *Nothobranchius melanospilus* were netted from the light grey turbid water. Every sweep in open water produced several specimens, while netting in vegetation produced more, up to 20 specimens per sweep.

Twenty days later in February (Figure 8), the pool was smaller and the water did not exceed 40 cm depth. *Nothobranchius melanospilus* (Figure 9) was present, but in lesser numbers. Only two or three specimens were caught per scoop of the net. Water scorpions and large diving beetles were caught with the fish.

Lukwale River

One Lukwale River site was investigated, located along the main road between Dar es Salaam and Kibiti to the

south. This site was a shallow depression under the bridge over the Lukwale River (Locality 'e' on Figure 1 and Table 1). The three species found by Nagy during the first visit in January were *Nothobranchius albimarginatus*, *Nothobranchius melanospilus* and what has been recently described as *Nothobranchius ruudwildekampi* (Costa, 2009). The pool was approximately 2 x 10 m and only about 30 cm deep.

In February there was more water (Figure 10). Collecting on the east side of the bridge produced only tadpoles about 8 cm long and barbs. The west side produced only small, newly-hatched tadpoles. No *Nothobranchius* were collected on either side of the bridge, but about 30 m from the main road and 2 m from the river bed, in a 30 cm deep hole, Horváth Kis collected *Nothobranchius ruudwildekampi*

Figure 8. Locality Yombo TZHK 09-2 (=TZN 09-2). Photo taken 1 February, 2009 by András Horváth Kis.

Figure 9. *Nothobranchius melanospilus* Yombo TZHK 09-2. Wild-caught male photo by András Horváth Kis.

Figure 10. Locality Lukwale River TZHK 09–3 (=TZN 09–8). Photo taken 2 February, 2009 by András Horváth Kis.

(Figure 11) and *Nothobranchius melanospilus*. These fishes had probably been washed out from the main habitat in the river bed by a flood and that seemed to be confirmed by the presence of the non-annual fishes and the newly-hatched tadpoles.

Mbezi River

The Mbezi River bridge, on the main road from Dar es Salaam southward towards Kibiti, is the type locality of *Nothobranchius luekei* and *Nothobranchius rubripinnis*. During the first visit in January, a temporary pool about 20 m in diameter and about 50 m from the road (Locality ‘F’ in Figure 1 and Table 1; Figure 12) yielded many *Nothobranchius melanospilus* in all parts of the pool, a few *Nothobranchius ruudwildekampi* and *Nothobranchius al-*

bimarginatus (Figure 13) in the shallows beneath overhanging grass, and *N. luekei* at the edges among the largest overhanging branches, a difficult place to access. The central and deeper parts of the pool held many 10 cm tadpoles.

Three weeks later in February 2009, the pool was slightly smaller but without significant change in volume or characteristics. Of the four species caught previously, only *Nothobranchius luekei* (Figures 14, 15) was found at the edges beneath the grass. Huge tadpoles were still present in numbers.

Jaribu

A large marsh with numerous pools parallels the western side of the main road from Dar es Salaam southward to Kibiti,

Figure 11 *Nothobranchius ruudwildekampi* Lukwale River TZHK 09–3. Wild-caught male. Photo by András Horváth Kis.

Figure 12. Locality Mbezi River TZN 09–9 (=TZHK 09–4). Photo taken 13 January, 2009 by Béla Nagy.

Figure 13. *Nothobranchius albimarginatus* Mbezi River TZN 09–9. Wild-caught male. Photo by Béla Nagy.

about 1 km north of Jaribu (Locality 'g' on Figure 1 and Table 1). Many juvenile to adult (10 cm) cichlids were collected during both visits. In January numerous *Nothobranchius ruudwildekampi* (Figure 16) were taken in a 30-50 cm deep and muddy water hole beside the swamp.

In February 2009, most of the pools at the edge of the swamp had dried. At one site about 8 cm deep, a few liters of light brown water remained and the bottom was covered with decayed leaves. From this remaining water Horváth Kis collected three *Nothobranchius ruudwildekampi*. The only other animals were leeches and snails.

Observations and discussion

Species numbers

The population structure of *Nothobranchius* habitats can change in a short

period of time. Half the sites we visited three weeks apart had reduced numbers of *Nothobranchius* species. In the other half, all the species persisted three weeks later but in reduced numbers. At one site, a pool close to dry still yielded a trio of specimens.

pH

Both Nagy and Horváth Kis measured water quality with a handheld Hanna Combo meter (Table 1). The water was generally alkaline; pH decreased in half the habitats, probably from the decay of aquatic vegetation.

Temperature

Temporary pools usually have a large surface area to volume ratio. The water temperature fluctuates with the elevation of the sun (Bronmar and Hansson, 2005) and temperature records reflect the time of day of measurement. We record-

Figure 14 *Nothobranchius luekei* Mbezi River TZHK 09–4. Wild-caught male. Photo by András Horváth Kis.

Figure 15. *Nothobranchius luekei* Mbezi River TZHK 09–4. Wild-caught female. Photo by András Horváth Kis

ed somewhat lower temperatures during January than February at just one locality, even though evaporating water should have heated faster as the pools dried out. Reduced water volume heats faster under the strong sun of the dry season. Shallow waters may rise to lethal temperatures for

some fish. Turbid water absorbs solar heat in the upper 5-6 cm of the water column, reducing the effect of the sun on lower layers (Williams, 2001). Many *Nothobranchius* habitats are often turbid and partly shaded by vegetation, both of which protect against overheating.

Figure 16. *Nothobranchius ruudwildekampi* Jaribu TZN 09–11. Wild-caught male. Photo by Béla Nagy.

Tolerance and Adaptation

Water quality varies more in temporary shallow pools than in larger and deeper water bodies, subject to the influences of turbidity and shade. The animals that live in temporary pools must have adapted to these conditions (Williams, 2001).

Although our measurements of water quality parameters changed during the three weeks between samples, the changes were not sufficient to cause disappearance of the species from the habitats. Others have reported the presence of *Nothobranchius* in other habitats where the changes in parameters were greater than recorded here.

Wild-caught *Nothobranchius* readily tolerate changes in water quality characteristics, and can be transferred to different quality water upon collection. Normal collection procedure is to transfer the fish in the field to plastic bags, and change water daily using available (and often quite

different) water sources and quality. The fishes usually tolerate these changes.

We conclude that water quality and changes in quality with time are not determining factors in the disappearance of *Nothobranchius* species from their natural habitats, as long as the changes do not reach lethal high temperatures or lethal low dissolved oxygen levels.

Why *Nothobranchius* disappear from drying pools

In the tropics, temporary wet season pools soon lose their water to evaporation (Hartland-Rowe, 1972). Most of the localities we studied had shrunk by the time of the second visit.

Nothobranchius often occupy pool margins among or under vegetation, or shallow embayments covered with leaf litter. These preferences held even when

the central and deeper parts of the pool would have been cooler. We presume the vegetated and leaf-littered portions of the pool not only protect against predation but offers more spawning habitat, essential for the survival of the fertilized eggs.

Sunlight on dry exposed soil can raise soil temperature to over 70 °C, sufficient to endanger killifish eggs (Johnson, 1993). Vegetation shades the soil and keeps it cooler and more suitable for development of the annual egg. As the dry season progresses, the habitats shrink and formerly protected zones at their fringe disappear. This loss of protective habitat may cause the loss of the fish to predation, as *Nothobranchius* are often lost from shrinking pools, even if they still contain water.

Based on our observations, we conclude the finding of *Nothobranchius* species in any pool at any single time varies with recent rainfall and the condition of the habitat. Heavy or frequent rain that causes river flooding might wash the natal *Nothobranchius* individuals hatched at that location out of the isolated pool, while also may wash in competing or predatory species from the adjacent river.

Presence of other fauna in the habitat

The dry phase of ephemeral ponds imposes a rigorous environment that only a few species can survive. Nevertheless, many freshwater species are successful (Wiggins et al., 1980).

In our investigations we typically found animals other than *Nothobranchius* species in the same pools, some larger than they, and predatory on annual and other fishes in these isolated habitats. Predation can explain why *Nothobranchius* can disap-

pear from a pond in two or three weeks, even though that pond still contains water. As the pond dries and the protective vegetation becomes remote, refuges disappear and predation increases.

Other fishes living in the same habitat also prey on *Nothobranchius*. We often found cichlids in these now-isolated pools, apparently washed in during river flooding (Nagy, 2008). If cichlids reach the habitat after flooding when young-of-year *Nothobranchius* have only recently hatched, the latter may be eliminated by predation. Others have reported the co-occurrence of large predatory *Nothobranchius* sharing the same pond with smaller prey species such as *Nothobranchius* (*Aphyobranchius*) species whose numbers are sustained by dense protective vegetation.

Conclusions

Adaptation to a single environmental stressor is not likely to ensure survival (Alderdice, 1972). Fishes successful in temporary aquatic habitats are likely to have adapted to a number of stressful environmental conditions. Minor variations in water quality alone are unlikely to determine survival. In our view, *Nothobranchius* species may have disappeared from suitable habitats because of loss of natural cover in the shrinking habitats and, as a consequence, increasingly successful predation.

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